

Workshop: Notes and Narratives, Music as a Cognitive Tool in ESL Learning

Proposed by: Yasamin Abedi

Step 1: Review TESL Canada syllabus (45 minutes)

TESL Canada's certification programs generally include:

Foundational knowledge: linguistics (phonology, syntax, semantics), second-language acquisition theories, e.g. Theories of second language acquisition include the Behaviorist Theory (Saville-Troike & Barto, 2019), Innatist Theory (Chomsky, 1965), Krashen's Monitor Model (Krashen, 1982), Cognitive Theory (McLaughlin, 1987), Interactionist Theory (Long, 1981), Sociocultural Theory (Lantolf & Thorne, 2006), Noticing Hypothesis (Schmidt, 1990), Competition Model (MacWhinney, 1989), and Connectionist Theory (Ellis, 2002).

Teaching skills: Lesson planning, classroom management, teaching methodologies (e.g., task-based, communicative approaches).

Cultural awareness: Sensitivity training for diverse ESL learners.

Assessment and feedback: Designing and implementing tests, evaluating progress.

Practicum: Supervised teaching experience

Step 2: Common Challenges in ESL Teaching and Training (20 minutes)

- Phonemic awareness: Difficulties in identifying and manipulating English phonemes (Derwing & Munro, 2015; Wang et al., 2023).
- Graphophonemic knowledge: Struggles with decoding complex letter-sound relationships in English (Perrachione et al., 2017).
- Pronunciation bias: Persistent accent and pronunciation errors impacting social integration (Munro, 2003; Derwing et al., 2021).
- Working memory deficits: Issues with retaining and processing new linguistic input during real-time tasks (Gathercole & Baddeley, 1990).
- Vocabulary retention: Weakness in long-term word recall due to limited contextual reinforcement (Schmitt, 2008).
- Cognitive overload: Difficulty managing multiple linguistic demands simultaneously (Sweller, 1988).
- Teacher training: Issues with ESL teachers that lack training in bilingual and inclusive strategies, with limited professional development, particularly in rural areas (Cummins et al., 2012).
- Academic language support: Many ESL learners achieve conversational fluency quickly but require structured, long-term support to develop academic English proficiency (CALP) (Cummins et al., 2012).

Step 3: Highlights from the Review of Literature (30 minutes)

- Improved pronunciation through rhythm training (Patel, 2011)
- Enhanced memory retention using music repetition (Moreno et al., 2009)
- Pitch sensitivity aiding stress and intonation recognition (Tierney & Kraus, 2013)

- Evidence of shared neural pathways between music and language (Koelsch, 2014; Patel, 2011).
- Studies
- Rhythm training enhances temporal processing (Tierney & Kraus, 2013).
- Songs improve emotional engagement and vocabulary retention (Pastuszek-Lipińska, 2024).

Activity:

Quick Demonstration: Play a clip– one melodic (musical) and one monotone. Ask participants to recall phrases from each clip to demonstrate music's mnemonic impact. <https://youtu.be/gZzKe1BC2XU>

Step 4: TESL and Music Integration (15 minutes)

Proposal: Adding music training as a module to equip ESL teachers with tools for:

1. Pronunciation improvement
2. Vocabulary retention via melody and rhythm

The strategy of using songs for enhancing language learning has been explored in a number of studies, especially in relation to phonological awareness, literacy, and early reading skills. Gromko (2005) shows a significant difference in phonological enhancement among kindergarten children with and without music lessons. During the treatment lessons, kindergarten children engaged in various music activities designed to enhance their understanding of rhythm and melody. They learned to sing new folk songs from diverse cultures and accompanied their singing with body percussion or kinesthetic movements, which reinforced steady beats, word rhythms, and pitch variations. The kinesthetic movements, often dancelike, helped organize their perceptions of musical sound in time and space.

Children also played instruments such as rhythm sticks, guiros, or xylophones to deepen their awareness of rhythm and melodic contour. Additionally, they interacted with graphic charts featuring dots, squares, or lines, which visually represented steady beats, word rhythms, and melodic contours, connecting their auditory and visual learning of music. These activities supported their development of musical literacy, akin to how beginning readers connect sounds to letters. These activities enhanced their spatial-temporal skills and literacy-related subtests, assessed through DIBELS posttests for letter-naming fluency, phoneme-segmentation, and nonsense-word fluency.

Moreover, employing music-based strategies to improve phonological skills has been discussed in contexts involving multilingual learners. Music training related to the Kodály curriculum is one of the activities used in such studies. This approach typically includes singing exercises, rhythmic clapping or tapping, melodic dictation, solfege (so-fa system), and ear training activities to help children improve their auditory processing, phonological awareness, and memory. These findings suggest that integrating music into language curricula can support language acquisition by enhancing phonemic awareness, a critical component of reading and overall literacy skills (Tierney et al., 2013).

Step 5: Practical Demonstration (2 hours)

A. Rhythm training for Phonological Awareness:

Exercise 1: Syllable clapping

Say a word (e.g., "banana"), clap for each syllable, and ask participants to do the same. Progress to multi-word phrases (e.g., "I love learning English").

Exercise 2: Stress and Intonation Drills

Use rhythmic tapping to show stressed syllables:

E.g., "She didn't take the money" (stress on take).

Pair tapping with walking to emphasize rhythm physically.

B. Pitch Training for Intonation:

Exercise 1: Singing scales for questions vs. statements

Have participants sing rising scales (questions) and falling scales (statements):

Rising: "Are you going?" (voice rises).

Falling: "I am going." (voice falls).

Exercise 2: Emotional Prosody Practice

Use a simple tune (e.g., "Twinkle, Twinkle") to convey different emotions:

Sing happily, sadly, or angrily, emphasizing tonal changes.

C. Song-Based Learning

The following Kodály-inspired list of songs is designed to enhance vocabulary, phonological awareness and memory in ESL/English language classes. Teachers are encouraged to incorporate melodies from various languages and cultures represented by their students, especially those from other cultures. These customized lyric adaptations are designed for use with simple, recognizable tunes across all proficiency

levels, from elementary to advanced, targeting the development of speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills through the mentioned cognitive enhancements.

Purpose: To help ESL learners improve syllable recognition, stress patterns, verbal retention and rhythmic timing in speech.

Vocabulary songs

Purpose: Teach words using melodies

For days of the week: "Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday..." (to "Frère Jacques" tune).

Encourage participants to create their own songs for ESL students, especially those who are from other cultures, languages or countries are encouraged to introduce their short folk or famous melodies to replace the lyrics with English words that are intended to be taught.

Mnemonic Phrases

Purpose: Link grammar rules to rhythmic chants, tapping, clapping or more stress for exceptions in the grammar rules

E.g., for verb conjugation: "He does, she does, but I **do**."

Grammar Practice

Purpose: To reinforce grammatical structures through repetitive and melodic patterns.

"This is the Way" (Traditional):

Focus: Present simple tense and daily routines.

Custom lyrics:

"This is the way **we brush our teeth**,

Brush our teeth, brush our teeth,

This is the way **we brush our teeth**,

Early in the morning."

Replace "brush our teeth" with other actions: "wash our hands," "read a book," etc.

"She'll Be Coming 'Round the Mountain":

Focus: Future tense.

Custom lyrics:

"**We will learn to speak** in English when we come, (clap, clap)

We will learn to speak in English when we come, (clap, clap)"

Adjust phrases to introduce other future-tense structures.

"Row, Row, Row Your Boat"

Focus: future perfect tense

You **will have learned** it,

By the end of the year,

Your grammar **will have improved**,

And your skills will be clear.

"Row, Row, Row Your Boat":

Focus: imperatives

Custom lyrics:

"Learn, learn, learn English fast,
Quickly as you go,
Pronounce, practice every day,
The best way to grow."

"The Wheels on the Bus":

Focus: imperatives

Custom lyrics:

"The teacher in the class says **'read your books,'**
Read your books, read your books.
The teacher in the class says **'read your books,'**
All through the school."

"Five Little Ducks":

Focus: Numbers and simple past tense.

Costume lyrics:

"Five little ducks **went out** one day,
Over the hill and far away,
Mother duck **said**, 'quack, quack, quack,'
But only four little ducks **came back**."

"Frère Jacques" (French):

Focus: present continuous, extension to he/she is, they are etc.

Custom lyrics:

"I am learning, I am learning,
English **now**, English **now**,
Singing helps me practice,
Singing helps me practice,
Every day, every day."

"Happy Birthday":

Focus: English tenses grammar

You **have learned** so much now,
Your skills are so bright,
You **have practiced** your grammar,
And you're doing it right!

Pronunciation and Prosody

Purpose: To improve pronunciation, stress, and intonation.

"Twinkle, Twinkle, Little Star":

Focus: Rising and falling intonation for questions vs. statements.

Questions: "Can you see the stars above?" (rising tone).

Statements: "Twinkle, twinkle, little star." (falling tone).

Memory and Retention

Purpose: To support retention of vocabulary, and phrases

"B-I-N-G-O" (Traditional Nursery Rhyme):

Focus: Syllable segmentation.

Custom lyrics: "There was a farmer, had a dog, and Bingo was his name-o. B-I-N-G-O..."

Replace "Bingo" with multi-syllable vocabulary words relevant to the lesson (e.g., "banana," "computer").

"If You're Happy and You Know It"

Focus: Sentence stress and emotions' vocabulary

"If you're (any feeling adjective) now, clap your hands!"

Emphasize stressed syllables through claps or stomps.

vocabulary in an engaging and memorable way.

"Mary Had a Little Lamb"

Focus: academic vocabulary, extension to any word

Custom lyrics:

Analyze and **evaluate**,

Use them every day,

Critical thinking guides you through,

In all you do and say

Synthesize and **summarize**,

Research to **explore**,

With academic terms like these,

You'll learn and grow much more.

Step 5: Feedback and Action Plan (30 minutes)

Discuss insights from the sessions.

Propose action steps:

- Advocate for TESL syllabus revision.
- Set up pilot programs in Canadian schools with support from local music teachers who are instructed to integrate Kodaly inspired melodies in ESL and any other English language learning classes.

References

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